

Research paper

Fostering pedagogical content knowledge on “probability” in preservice primary teachers within formal teacher education: A longitudinal experimental field study

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Pedagogical content knowledge

Mathematics

Probability

Preservice teacher

Teacher education

Intervention study

ABSTRACT

The article investigates the promotion of pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) on “probability”, which has recently become part of the primary school curriculum in Switzerland, during formal teacher training. In a longitudinal experimental field study with 512 prospective primary school teachers, a series of multiple regression analyses showed more favorable PCK development in all four treatment groups compared to a control group. The effects of the treatments proved to be independent of the initial cognitive preconditions. Given that all four treatments proved to be equally effective, there appear to be various effective ways to promote the acquisition of PCK on probability.

1. Introduction

Research on teachers’ professional knowledge often draws a distinction between pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), content knowledge (CK), and pedagogical knowledge (PK), in line with Shulman (1986, 1987). In the present paper, we focus on CK, and in particular on PCK. While the former encompasses knowledge of the domain itself (Krauss, Brunner, et al., 2008), the latter refers to knowledge about how to make the subject matter accessible to pupils (Depaepe, Verschaffel, & Kelchtermans, 2013). PCK has a crucial influence on the quality of instruction and on pupils’ learning (e.g., Baumert et al., 2010; Depaepe, Verschaffel, & Star, 2020; H. C. Hill, Rowan, & Ball, 2005; Sadler, Sonnert, Coyle, Cook-Smith, & Miller, 2013). Several studies have comparatively examined the predictive power of PCK and CK with regard to the development of learners’ achievement (in biology or mathematics) using multilevel analyses, with the results revealing a greater predictive power of PCK compared to CK. The stronger predictive power of PCK was demonstrated either as a direct effect (Mahler, Großschedl, & Harms, 2017) or as an indirect effect mediated by cognitive activation (Baumert et al., 2010; Förtsch, Werner, von Kotzebue, & Neuhaus, 2016)

or by individual learning support (Baumert et al., 2010). Accordingly, Baumert et al. (2010) stated that “it is PCK and not CK that has the decisive impact on key aspects of instructional quality – namely, cognitive activation and individual learning support – and thus on student progress” (p. 158).

Given that PCK and CK can be learned (Blömeke & Delaney, 2014), fostering them is one of the core tasks of (formal) teacher education (Ball, Hill, & Bass, 2005; Berry, Depaepe, & Van Driel, 2016; Friedrichsen et al., 2009; Grossman, 1990; Kleickmann et al., 2013; Shulman, 1986, 1987). For instance, studies have shown that preservice teachers possess more PCK on mathematics at the end of their teacher education than at the beginning (Blömeke, Buchholtz, Suhl, & Kaiser, 2014; Buchholtz & Kaiser, 2013; Kleickmann et al., 2013). Various sources for the development of PCK have been discussed (Evens, Elen, & Depaepe, 2015; Grossman, 1990; Shulman, 1986, 1987). To date, research in this area mostly consists of qualitative studies or quantitative studies with small samples (Depaepe et al., 2013; Evens et al., 2015; Schneider & Plasman, 2011). Experimental and/or longitudinal studies on the development of PCK are rare, but have long been called for (Depaepe et al., 2020; Evens et al., 2015).

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2025.104953>

Received 9 December 2023; Received in revised form 8 June 2024; Accepted 27 January 2025

Available online 14 March 2025

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As in many other countries, in Switzerland, the topic of “probability” has only recently become part of the primary school curriculum (cf. Langrall, 2018). The topic is seen as being hard to understand and difficult to teach (Batanero & Diaz, 2012; Jones, Langrall, & Mooney, 2007). Accordingly, sufficient PCK (and CK) on this topic is especially important for preservice teachers (Stohl, 2005). To date, few studies have examined how PCK on probability can be fostered in preservice teachers as part of formal teacher education (Batanero, Chernoff, Engel, Lee, & Sánchez, 2016). In particular, there is a lack of studies addressing which instructional settings are particularly conducive to the acquisition of PCK. To the best of our knowledge, despite the stated clear need for such research, no study to date has investigated how PCK on the topic of “probability” can most effectively be fostered in primary teacher education (cf. Batanero, 2020; Batanero et al., 2016; Eichler & Vogel, 2014; Jones et al., 2007; Shaughnessy, 1992; Stohl, 2005). In view of the limited understanding of how to foster PCK on probability in primary teacher education, the present experimental longitudinal study was conducted with four measurement time points, four treatment groups, and one control group. The main aim was to answer the following three questions:

1. Do the treatment groups show a more favorable development of PCK on probability compared to the control group?
2. Does PCK on probability develop more favorably in some treatment groups than in others?
3. Do cognitive preconditions (PCK, CK, intelligence, all at T1) moderate the effects of the individual treatments?

In the following sections, we first clarify the construct of PCK (Section 2) and then discuss how PCK can be fostered in formal teacher education (Section 3). Section 4 addresses difficulties in learning and teaching the topic of “probability” and discusses studies examining PCK on probability and how it is fostered. Based on this, Section 5 develops design principles for course development on the topic of “PCK on probability”. Drawing on these design principles, Section 6 describes the intervention in detail.

Hereinafter, we use the term “pupils” for learners at school, “students” for learners in teacher education, and “learners” to refer to both pupils and students.

2. Pedagogical content knowledge

2.1. What is PCK?

Based on Shulman (1986, 1987), various conceptualizations of PCK have been developed (e.g., Ball, Thames, & Phelps, 2008; Krauss, Baumert, & Blum, 2008; for an overview of different conceptions, see, e.g. Depaepe et al., 2013), the majority of which encompass the following two subcomponents (albeit sometimes with different names): *knowledge of students’ (mis)conceptions* and *knowledge of instructional strategies and representations* (Depaepe et al., 2013; Shulman, 1986). The latter include, in particular, suitable representations of the mathematical facts, good explanations, analogies and examples, as well as knowledge about what makes learning the content difficult or easy. Further sub-components are sometimes added, in particular *curricular knowledge* (e.g., Grossman, 1990; Tatto et al., 2008) or knowledge of mathematical tasks (Krauss, Brunner, et al., 2008).

A further distinction is drawn between two complementary perspectives on PCK (Depaepe et al., 2013; Kaiser et al., 2017): the cognitive perspective (rather theoretical, declarative knowledge) and the situated perspective (knowledge about actions in a specific instructional context). It can be assumed that theoretical, declarative knowledge is rather acquired in formal teacher education, whereas situated knowledge is rather acquired in teaching practica and in later professional practice. In the current study, the three subcomponents of PCK presented above in italics are considered from a primarily cognitive

perspective.

2.2. PCK and CK

The question of whether CK and PCK can be empirically separated into two different dimensions of professional competence essentially depends on their respective conceptualization (Copur-Gencturk & Tolar, 2022). From a cognitive perspective, PCK and CK can be seen as theoretically distinguishable and empirically differentiable facets of teachers’ professional knowledge, which has also been demonstrated in empirical studies. For instance, with data on preservice primary teachers from the Teacher Education and Development in Mathematics (TEDS-M) study, Blömeke, Houang, and Suhl (2014) showed, using multidimensional and multiple-group IRT models, that the latent two-dimensional model (CK versus PCK) had a better model fit than the one-dimensional model (see also Copur-Gencturk & Tolar, 2022; Kleickmann et al., 2015; Krauss, Brunner, et al., 2008).

In all conceptualizations, CK is seen as central to the development of PCK (Berry et al., 2016; Blömeke, Suhl, Kaiser, & Döhrmann, 2012; Kleickmann et al., 2013; Tröbst et al., 2018). Many consider CK as a necessary but not sufficient prerequisite for the acquisition of PCK (Ball et al., 2005; Depaepe et al., 2013, 2015; Evens et al., 2015; Friedrichsen et al., 2009; Kunter et al., 2013). Indeed, in a study examining CK and PCK on rational numbers in elementary and lower secondary teachers, using logistic regression, Depaepe et al. (2015) found that PCK items were generally more difficult to answer than the corresponding CK items in related CK-PCK item pairs. From this, the authors concluded that CK is a necessary but not sufficient condition for the development of PCK. In an experimental study, Tröbst et al. (2018) investigated the optimal order of instruction of CK, PCK, and PK with respect to the acquisition of PCK on the topic of “fractions” in preservice primary school teachers. The results revealed that there are several effective ways to foster PCK, but that teacher education programs with early and explicit PCK instruction are particularly beneficial for the development of PCK (Tröbst et al., 2018).

3. How can the acquisition of PCK be fostered in formal teacher education?

3.1. Sources of PCK in teacher education

There are various ways in which teachers can acquire PCK (Blömeke, Kaiser, & Lehmann, 2010; Krauss, Baumert, & Blum, 2008; Magnusson, Krajcik, & Borko, 1999; Tröbst et al., 2018; Van Driel & Berry, 2012), and various sources are used for this purpose (Evens et al., 2015; Friedrichsen et al., 2009; Grossman, 1990; Shulman, 1987). Table 1 shows eight possible and often discussed sources of PCK that were used to design the treatments in the present intervention study.

3.2. Empirical findings on fostering the acquisition of PCK

Overall, the empirical findings on fostering PCK appear contradictory. On the one hand, there is evidence that PCK can be promoted even by means of temporally short training consisting of a few hours. For example, in the aforementioned experimental study by Tröbst et al. (2018), comprising three treatment groups and two control groups with four measurement points, based on a series of explanatory item-response models, the authors demonstrated that a 7-h intervention spread across two consecutive days can have a positive effect on the development of PCK (and CK) on fractions and fractional arithmetic in prospective primary school teachers.

On the other hand, it has become clear that intervention studies to foster PCK do not always show significant effects. In an experimental study by Santagata, Kersting, Givvin, and Stigler (2010), for example, which included one treatment group and one control group and employed pre- and post-tests, regression analyses revealed that the

Table 1
Eight sources of PCK in teacher education.

<p>PCK courses: Specific courses within formal teacher education are essential for the acquisition of PCK (Evens et al., 2015; Grossman, 1990) and enable PCK and CK to be fostered simultaneously (Appova & Taylor, 2020). Such courses can include the following features: good tasks, different content representations and materials (including virtual), appropriate language, professional resources such as curricula and teaching materials, good practice examples, as well as evidence-based suggestions from research (Appova & Taylor, 2020; Van Driel & Berry, 2012).</p>
<p>Disciplinary background: As mentioned in Section 2.2, CK can be considered as crucial for the acquisition of PCK (Evens et al., 2015; Grossman, 1990).</p>
<p>Apprenticeship of observation: An individual's own past experiences as a learner in school or in teacher education can also contribute to the acquisition of PCK (Grossman, 1990).</p>
<p>Planning and reflection: Planning and reflecting on teaching are seen as central for the acquisition of PCK (Evens et al., 2015; Friedrichsen et al., 2009; Schneider, 2013). Reflection can refer both to own's own teaching and to other aspects of teacher activities (e.g., analyzing teaching materials or one's own task solution paths). However, sufficient CK is necessary for both planning and reflection (Parkison, 2009; Sibbald, 2009). Moreover, not all reflection leads to more PCK; rather, it appears that reflection needs to induce a "higher level of thinking" (Monet & Etkina, 2008, p. 470). Further important factors include appropriate questions to guide the reflection processes (Kenney, Shoffner, & Norris, 2013; Michalsky, 2012) as well as good guidance for planning (Stender, Brückmann, & Neumann, 2017).</p>
<p>Curricular material: A further source for the acquisition of PCK is curricular material, e.g., textbooks and teacher commentary (Ball & Cohen, 1996; E. A. Davis, Janssen, & Van Driel, 2016; Friedrichsen et al., 2009; Grossman & Thompson, 2008; Schneider, 2013), and in particular educative curricular material (E. A. Davis & Krajcik, 2005; J. D. Davis, 2009), which has been specifically designed for the purpose of teachers' learning. However, working with curricular material does not automatically lead to the acquisition of more CK and/or PCK (Collopy, 2003; Remillard, 2000). The (subject-specific) quality of the material (J. D. Davis, 2009; Kesidou & Roseman, 2002) as well as the visibility of pupils' thinking contained therein appear to be crucial (Remillard, 2000).</p>
<p>Tasks: Good tasks are likewise viewed as relevant for the acquisition of PCK (Appova & Taylor, 2020; Ashline & Quinn, 2009; Suzuka et al., 2009; Tirosh, Tsamir, Levenson, & Tabach, 2011), and can simultaneously foster both CK and PCK (Appova & Taylor, 2020; Watson & Mason, 2007). Working with tasks in teacher education can have various objectives (Watson & Mason, 2007; Watson & Sullivan, 2008; Zaslavsky, 2007). For example, the focus can be on understanding subject-specific concepts, representations, and materials, as well as on linguistic tools and curricular aspects. A further focus might be on the possibilities and challenges of implementing tasks in the classroom, especially in terms of anticipating and analyzing typical pupil answers (cf. Ball et al., 2005). According to Suzuka et al. (2009), it seems essential to address how to deal with tasks in the classroom. Solving tasks and working with teaching materials do not automatically lead to learning; rather, reflection is also fundamental in this regard (Watson & Mason, 2007; Watson & Sullivan, 2008).</p>
<p>Learning from experience: Teaching experience, and especially experiencing the reactions of pupils in the classroom, is deemed particularly important for the acquisition and consolidation of PCK (Evens et al., 2015; Grossman, 1990; Hattie, 2012; Timperley, 2013). However, on the whole, the empirical findings in this regard are somewhat ambivalent (e.g., Copur-Gencturk & Li, 2023; Friedrichsen et al., 2009; Kleickmann et al., 2013; Lee, Brown, Luft, & Roehrig, 2007). In the case of preservice primary school teachers, it appears that teaching experience in combination with corresponding formal education fosters the acquisition of PCK (Capraro, Capraro, Parker, Kulm, & Raulerson, 2005; Strawhecker, 2005), with reflection on the experience being vital in this regard (Timperley, 2013).</p>
<p>Core components of understanding: "Core components of understanding" refer to "the sub-elements of a concept that the individual needs to have understood, and linked together in order to understand the concept as a whole" (Drollinger-Vetter, 2011, p. 212). The approach of "Core components of understanding" draws on the considerations of Aebli (1994, 2001), according to which teachers' in-depth knowledge needs to unfold in order to make it accessible for the pupils (see also Dröse & Prediger, 2023; Hiebert & Grouws, 2007; Morris, Hiebert, & Spitzer, 2009). The idea of unfolding stems from a cognitive psychological perspective on learning, according to which semantic networks are formed as concepts are learned (Aebli, 1994). When this network of concepts unfolds, in the conceptualization of Drollinger-Vetter (2011), not only typical subject-specific aspects are considered, but also typical misconceptions on the part of the learners. For instance, in the case of the topic of "probability", one needs to have understood, among other things, that the result of the next throw of a die cannot be predicted or influenced (provided that the die is fair). If students get to know the core components of understanding regarding a concept and work with them, this should, according to Drollinger-Vetter (2011) promote the acquisition of PCK on this concept. To understand a concept, it further appears to be important that the core components of understanding and their connections with each other are clearly and coherently carved out in the instruction: Drollinger-Vetter (2011) demonstrated that coherent teaching in this regard is associated with higher pupil achievements in mathematics.</p>

intervention had no influence on the development of PCK (or CK) in mathematics among in-service elementary teachers (see also Buchholtz & Kaiser, 2013).

From a methodological perspective, the following shortcomings are noteworthy (cf. for example Evens et al., 2015): a) there are few experimental studies, b) delayed post-tests are rare, c) the studies mostly use small samples, d) different PCK sources are often used simultaneously. Accordingly, researchers have called for experimental intervention studies, which include a delayed post-test and larger sample sizes, to (comparatively) examine the effect of different learning opportunities or sources on PCK acquisition (Depaepe et al., 2020; Evens et al., 2015; Rosenkränzer, Hörsch, Schuler, & Riess, 2017).

4. The topic of "probability" in primary teacher education

The topic of "probability" is seen as difficult to understand (Batanero & Diaz, 2012; Batanero et al., 2016; Jones et al., 2007). In part, this is due to the idiosyncrasies of the topic, e.g., different approaches to probability, especially classical (theoretical) and frequentist (empirical) probability (cf. Eichler & Vogel, 2014). Moreover, these difficulties are compounded by the hard-to-grasp issue that "Random phenomena are characterized by having short-term unpredictability and long-term stability" (Jones et al., 2007, p. 918). Difficulties in understanding the topic are well evidenced in all age groups – even among teachers – and often persist even after attending specialized instruction (Batanero et al., 2016; Jones et al., 2007; Shaughnessy, 1992; based especially on fundamental research by Piaget & Inhelder, 1975, as well as Fischbein, 1975 and Tversky & Kahneman, 1974).

The topic of "probability" is likewise seen as difficult to teach (Batanero & Diaz, 2012; Dollard, 2011; Greer, 2014). Teachers show a tendency to skip past it in their lessons (Jones et al., 2007; Shaughnessy, 1992), partly due to the dual uncertainty that they have to endure when teaching this topic (Batanero et al., 2016): The ever-present uncertainty inherent in any interaction between teacher, pupils, and lesson content (Costache, Becker, Staub, & Mainhard, 2019) and the uncertainty due to the unpredictability of probability experiments.

Compared to other mathematics topics, there is still a lack of knowledge regarding what teachers know, or need to know, regarding probability and how to teach it (Batanero & Álvarez-Arroyo, 2024; Batanero et al., 2016; Eichler & Vogel, 2014; Jones et al., 2007; Shaughnessy, 1992).

With regard to *studies on CK*, all of the studies which we considered relevant and reviewed in detail – encompassing both pre- and in-service teachers and all school levels – demonstrated that teachers possess limited CK on the topic of "probability" (e.g., Arican & Kuzu, 2020; Canada, 2006; Dollard, 2011; Gómez-Torres, Batanero, Díaz, & Contreras, 2016; Hourigan & Leavy, 2020). Often, teachers have the same misconceptions as their pupils (e.g., Dollard, 2011; Liu & Thompson, 2007; Stohl, 2005). Studies examining the promotion of CK have yielded ambiguous findings: While it is known that many teachers show misconceptions despite specialist teaching (see above), Canada (2006) demonstrated that at least certain conceptions can be changed through an intervention. Only after the data collection for the present study was there a particular increase in research on CK regarding "probability", employing more comprehensive and statistically validated instruments, especially in primary teachers (see for example Arican & Kuzu, 2020;

Gómez-Torres et al., 2016).

With regard to *studies on PCK*, little is known about primary teachers' PCK on the topic of "probability" (Batanero, 2020; Batanero et al., 2016; Stohl, 2005). The few studies available (Ives, 2009; Swenson, 1998) – with (very) small samples – revealed that teachers possess little PCK, with deficits evident in all three subcomponents of PCK (cf. Section 2.1). For instance, it was shown that teachers often did not know how to apply materials and simulations in their lessons on probability in a way that would foster pupils' understanding (Callingham & Watson, 2011; Stohl, 2005). Moreover, knowledge about pupils' conceptions regarding the topic was often lacking (Swenson, 1998).

Regarding *studies on fostering PCK in teacher education*, similarly, barely any studies so far have examined the promotion of PCK on the topic of "probability" in preservice teachers (Batanero, 2020; Batanero & Diaz, 2012; Batanero et al., 2016; Stohl, 2005). The limited available knowledge on fostering PCK largely stems from case studies using interviews and classroom observation among *in-service teachers* (Peng, 2007; Yarbrough, Daane, & Vessel, 1998). The results of these studies suggest that the acquisition of PCK can be positively influenced by specialist courses; this presumably also applies to preservice teachers.

5. Course content and design principles for course development on the topic of "PCK on probability"

In view of Sections 3 and 4, in the following, we formulate considerations for the design of effective courses to foster PCK from a subject-specific (Section 5.1; course content) and cross-subject perspective (Section 5.2; design principles).

As the current study was implemented in the framework of regular preservice teacher education, it was necessary to take the following two institutional framework conditions into account:

1. Primary teacher education lasts for three years and encompasses seven school subjects. Therefore, there is little time available to tackle particular topics within the courses (e.g., probability).
2. In the same courses, both PCK- and CK-related contents are taught.

Table 2
Course contents on fostering PCK on the topic of "probability".

Starting point PCK-based requirements for primary school teaching	
The primary school pupil should gain experience of random phenomena and learn central concepts by carrying out experiments and simulations and using suitable subject-specific representations (Batanero & Diaz, 2012; Langrall & Mooney, 2005). The classical and frequentist approach to probability should already be taught at primary level (Dollard, 2011; Eichler & Vogel, 2014; Jones et al., 2007; Stohl, 2005; but see also Devlin, 2014).	
Contents of the courses on fostering PCK (and CK) derived from the upper part of this table in preservice teacher education (see in particular Batanero, 2015; Batanero & Diaz, 2012; Batanero et al., 2016; Chernoff & Zazkis, 2011; Dollard, 2011; Eichler & Vogel, 2013; Hourigan & Leavy, 2020; Jones et al., 2007; Stohl, 2005)	
Pedagogical content knowledge	Content knowledge
Contents (PCK and CK are closely aligned) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-concepts and typical errors of learners • Knowledge on planning and efficiently implementing experiments and simulations in the classroom • Dealing with age group-appropriate experiments and simulations in the classroom in a way that is conducive to learning and time-efficient • Curricular knowledge (contents of primary level, importance and use) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Particularities of the content compared to other mathematical topics (e.g., the different approaches to probability) • Prototypical examples on classical and frequentist approach to probability as well as the relationship between the two (including experiments and simulations) • Central probability-specific terms and representations (e.g., probability scales)
Conceptualizations of PCK and CK <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive perspective, three PCK components: see Section 2.1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Close to curriculum: Focus on secondary school level and gambling context • The CK that is necessary for acquiring PCK
Methods	Students should be taught in a way that is similar to how they will later teach children in the classroom (positive version of the apprenticeship of observation, see Section 3.1 as well as Even & Markovits, 1993): Students should be confronted with their own conceptions, conduct experiments and simulations themselves, solve typical textbook tasks on probability, and reflect on them from a PCK- and CK-based perspective. In this way, CK and PCK can develop simultaneously.

5.1. PCK-based perspective on the design of courses

The starting point for designing the courses was the PCK-based requirements regarding the contents and methods of primary school teaching on the topic of "probability" (Table 2 upper part: PCK-based requirements for primary school teaching). In particular, these include the importance of experiments and simulations as well as the requirement to employ both the classical and frequentist approach to probability within the instruction (cf., e.g., Eichler & Vogel, 2014). The latter is deemed important in order to be able to counter the difficulties in learning probability described in Section 4. From these requirements, we derived the CK- and PCK-related contents to be considered for teacher education, their conceptualizations, as well as methodological approaches (Table 2 lower part: Preservice teacher education).

5.2. Design principles for creating instructional settings

Table 3 shows principles for designing instructional settings that are independent of the topic of "probability". They are based on the considerations and findings on fostering PCK presented in Section 3. If different teaching settings are to be compared in terms of their effectiveness, for reasons of fairness it is also important to ensure that *all* students in *all* settings have the same opportunity to learn (OTL) (as far as possible).

6. The intervention

The intervention in the present study was based on four instructional settings.

6.1. Instructional settings

The four instructional settings were developed under consideration of the reflections on designing courses to foster PCK on the topic of "probability" (cf. Section 5, Tables 2 and 3). Each of the four instructional settings has a specific or exclusive emphasis on one PCK source. The different sources are described in detail in Section 3.1. Table 4 depicts the four sources and describes their assumed effect with regard to PCK acquisition.

Table 3
Design principles of instructional settings.

Design principles	Description	
PCK and CK OTL identical	PCK and CK should be fostered, as far as possible, to the same extent in all instructional settings: The OTL should be the same for all students in all settings.	
Independence from prior knowledge	The instructional settings should be as independent from students' prior PCK and CK on probability as possible, so that no group of students is at an advantage or disadvantage.	
Several PCK sources	The instructional settings should encompass several PCK sources to enable an optimally large OTL. Based on Section 3.1, these may in particular be <i>PCK course, curricular material, planning, core components of understanding, tasks and learning from experience as well as the two sources below.</i>	
	<i>Apprenticeship of observation</i>	Apprenticeship of observation can be used in a positive sense: The students should be taught, as far as possible, in a similar manner to how they should later teach children in the classroom (cf. Table 2).
	<i>Reflection</i>	Reflection on the problem-solving, the contents and methods is at the heart of the courses because reflection is seen as essential in all PCK sources.
Reduction of complexity	Simplifications are necessary to allow the students to concentrate on the central aspects of the practices of a profession (similarly to "approximation of practice" in line with Grossman et al., 2009, p. 2058). Not only does this apply to teaching itself, but it is especially important for planning and for working with teaching materials.	
Guidance	To acquire PCK and CK, students need suitable guidance and leadership (see also Stender et al., 2017), similar to the needs of pupils (Even & Markovits, 1993). In particular, this is the case when working in the courses or when planning and reflecting.	
Transfer to regular teacher education	A transfer of the instructional settings to courses of regular teacher education should be possible: The employed methods, materials, and duration of the intervention should fit into the existing regular teacher education structures.	

Note: The principles assume that PCK and CK are taught simultaneously in the instructional settings.

Table 4
Four PCK sources and their effect on the acquisition of PCK.

PCK source	Why does the source contribute to the acquisition of PCK?
Tasks	The assumption is that a broader variety of tasks as well as tasks in different contexts, which are carefully worked on and reflected upon, enable more diverse insights into different PCK-related aspects and in this way contribute to the acquisition of PCK.
Core components of understanding	The assumption is that the explicit and detailed treatment of the core components of understanding supports the understanding of the pupils' reflections and the recognition of the challenges in working with curricular material. Doing so also promotes PCK acquisition.
Learning from experience	The assumption is that, in particular, feedback from pupils and seeing what works with pupils fosters the acquisition of PCK. To reduce complexity, teaching experience was gathered in a 1:1 setting, which is why this instructional setting is subsequently called "Tutorial situation".
Curricular material	The assumption is that by analyzing the approaches in the curricular material, important PCK-related content aspects become apparent, thus contributing to the acquisition of PCK.

6.2. Introduction and Consolidation

The topic of "probability" is seen as particularly challenging and we started from the assumption that the vast majority of preservice teachers possess little prior knowledge on this topic (cf. Section 4). Based on Aebli's theory of building cognitive structures (Aebli, 1994, 2001), we further assumed that an intervention comprising an introduction, followed by a consolidation that builds on this introduction, should be conducive to the acquisition of PCK. The Introduction and Consolidation each lasted for half a day (total duration of intervention: eight lessons), which roughly corresponds to the time available for this topic in primary school teacher education (ecological validity of the intervention). In the Introduction, which took place on the first day of the intervention, the central PCK- and CK-related contents were taught and practiced (see Table 2). In the Consolidation, which took place on the second day, two tasks from the Introduction were used for the purpose of planning, implementation, and reflection. Table 5 presents the differences and similarities between the Introduction and Consolidation, and the different phases of the Consolidation, with respect to aims, contents, and methods.

Note that the content and methodology listed in Table 5 were identical for all students. In particular, all students had an identical set of PCK sources.

6.2.1. Introduction

The Introduction took two different forms, with a distinction made between the instructional settings "Core components of understanding" and "Tasks". The difference between these two instructional settings lay

in how the identical central PCK and CK contents were addressed:

Instructional setting "Core components of understanding": In this setting, the core components of understanding and their connections were introduced and elaborated more explicitly and frequently, with the help of a small number of tasks, which were analyzed in a differentiated manner.

Instructional setting "Tasks": In this setting, the PCK- and CK-related contents were introduced and elaborated with the help of a larger variety of tasks and from several different contexts, which corresponds to a commonly used approach in teacher education.

To ensure that the OTL was as similar as possible across the two settings (see Table 3), both settings featured the essential core components of understanding. Likewise, both included an identical set of tasks on which students worked. The difference lay in the fact that, in addition, each instructional setting focused more on one particular PCK source: *core components of understanding* or *tasks*.

6.2.2. Consolidation

No new PCK or CK contents were introduced in the Consolidation. All students carried out planning, implementation, and reflection individually. As with the Introduction, the Consolidation also took two forms: "Tutorial situation" and "Curricular material".

Instructional setting "Tutorial situation": The students taught the previously planned teaching unit with one pupil in a 1:1 situation.

Instructional setting "Curricular material": The students compared their planning with teaching materials that addressed the two tasks from the planning phase.

For students in their third semester, all consolidation activities are

Table 5
Differences and similarities between the Introduction and Consolidation.

	Introduction	Consolidation
Day (duration)	Intervention Day 1 (4 lessons)	Intervention Day 2 (4 lessons)
Aim of course	Familiarization with the central PCK- and CK-related contents	Consolidation of the Introduction using two tasks from the Introduction
Course leaders and their role	Experienced lecturers for mathematics education, who have completed a four-day training program (see Section 8.2) Teaching PCK and CK	Exclusive organization of the procedures
Content focus	broad: important PCK- and CK-related contents from Kindergarten to 6th grade (with experiments and simulations)	narrow: <u>Two tasks of 5th grade, which were addressed in the Introduction</u>
Type of instruction	Lecturer-led but also comprised small group or individual work	Independent written work (exception see Table 6)
Structure of the course (presented in simplified form)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theoretical introduction part 1 (also contains short work tasks for students) • Working on tasks in groups: Conducting experiments and the corresponding simulations, recording, presenting results, and reflecting • Plenary discussion on the essential findings from the tasks • Theoretical introduction part 2 (also contains short work tasks for students) • Final discussion 	<p>Planning (45 min)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent planning of a 45-min teaching unit for one pupil from the 5th grade on two predetermined tasks • <u>Material from the first day can be used</u> <hr/> <p>Implementation (45 min) Implementation of the two tasks from the planning</p> <hr/> <p>Reflection (45 min) <u>Guided by concrete content-related prompts</u></p>
Shared PCK sources	<i>PCK course, disciplinary background, tasks, reflection, apprenticeship of observation</i>	<i>Planning and reflection</i>

Note. underlined: Measures to reduce complexity.

challenging. To facilitate an optimal utilization of the inherent learning potential and to avoid overwhelming the students, various measures were adopted: The students dealt with *two tasks*, which had already been addressed in the *Introduction, from a PCK- and a CK-based perspective*. Additionally, they were provided with a *planning grid*, which helped to make PCK and CK explicit and also *outlined the prior knowledge to be expected in the age group under focus*. Students were able to use all *documents from the first day of the intervention*, and the *reflection was guided by targeted questions with the same structure in both instructional settings*. These measures to reduce complexity also served to render the OTL as comparable as possible across the two settings. The planning and reflection phase were identical in the two instructional settings. The difference lay in the implementation of the plan, which lasted for 45 min.

Thus, all four instructional settings have the same PCK- and CK-related contents and shared a common core of PCK sources (cf. Table 5). However, each focused on *one specific* source in particular (cf. Table 6).

6.3. Treatments

By intersecting the two instructional settings of the Introduction – “Core components of understanding” (CU) and “Tasks” (TA) – and the two instructional settings of the Consolidation – “Tutorial situation” (TS) and “Curricular material” (CM) – four treatments were developed: CUTS, CUCM, TATS, TACM.

Table 6
The four instructional settings.

	Introduction		Consolidation	
Instructional setting	“Core components of understanding”	“Tasks”	“Tutorial situation”	“Curricular material”
Abbreviation	CU	TA	TS	CM
Design according to Table 5, with specific focus on	Explicit and repeated working out of the core components of understanding	Working with diverse tasks from different contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning • Implementation: Teaching the plan with <i>one pupil</i> • Reflection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning • Implementation: Compare the plan with curricular material • Reflection
Difference	Way in which CK and PCK are taught		Implementation phase: Teaching versus comparing	

Note. The name of the instructional setting already contains that of the PCK source which characterizes the respective setting (cf. Section 3.1), with the exception of the setting “Tutorial situation”, where the concern is with the PCK source *learning from experience*.

7. The present study

Based on the considerations outlined above, the following shortcomings in previous research can be discerned:

First, as the topic of “probability” has only recently become part of the primary school curriculum – both in Switzerland and internationally – research findings on fostering PCK on this topic in teacher education are still scarce. In particular, there is a lack of quantitative empirical studies on fostering PCK on probability in preservice primary teachers.

Second, with regard to fostering PCK in general, there is a dearth of research with an experimental and/or longitudinal design. In particular, there is a lack of studies examining the effectiveness of several PCK sources from a comparative perspective. Moreover, many of the previous studies were based on small samples, and the studies only partially considered background characteristics that are relevant for the acquisition of PCK.

The present experimental, longitudinal field study with four treatment groups and one control group, and four data collections (T1–T4), attempted to address these shortcomings.

Based on the three research questions (Section 1) and the considerations outlined above (Sections 3-6), the following hypotheses were formulated:

Hypothesis 1. PCK on probability will develop more favorably in all treatment groups compared to the control group.

Hypothesis 2. PCK on probability will develop more favorably in the

Table 7
Design of the study.

	Treatment groups	Control group
Information from the course administration of the “Primary Education” program (before the start of the study)	Gender, educational background, cohort Allocation of students to the individual treatments and the control group	
Baseline Data collection T1 (one day before start of intervention)	PCK, CK, intelligence, mathematics self-concept	
Day 1 Morning Intervention	<i>Introduction instructional settings</i> “Core components of understanding” vs. “Tasks”	Experimentation – discover mathematics Part 1
Day 1 Afternoon Data collection T2	PCK	
Day 2 Morning Intervention	<i>Consolidation instructional settings</i> “Tutorial situation” vs. “Curricular material”	Experimentation – discover mathematics Part 2
Day 2 Afternoon Data collection T3	PCK	
Follow-up Data collection T4 (approx. 10 weeks later)	PCK	

Note. The follow-up was carried out as part of the course “Mathematics education”.

treatment group CUTS than in the other treatment groups.

The OTL was broadly the same in both Introduction settings and both Consolidation settings: Both settings of the Introduction contained the essential core components of understanding and a same set of typical tasks. Both settings of the Consolidation comprised planning, implementation, and reflection. Moreover, in the respective implementation, all students received feedback on their planning as well as an insight into pupils’ thinking.

The second hypothesis derives from previous findings that students have little prior knowledge on this difficult topic (see Section 4). Therefore, on the first day of the intervention, they received thorough preparation for the second day, and on the second day, complexity was purposely reduced at various points (see Section 6.2). In our view, the superiority of the CUTS treatment lies in the *combination* of the two instructional settings CU and TS. The CU setting featured a more explicit and deeper focus on core components of understanding than the TA setting, but included fewer tasks, thus adopting a thematically narrower perspective than the TA setting. In the TS setting, the students received direct feedback on their planning based on the pupils’ reactions and a *more realistic* insight into an individual pupil’s thinking. By contrast, students in the CM setting had to derive their own feedback on their planning by comparing it with the approaches of others; these comparisons thus only provided an indirect insight into pupils’ thinking. However, they had the advantage of being able to get to know various approaches, and they did not have to react immediately.

Overall, we assume that the more explicit and focused approach in the instructional setting CU, *in combination* with the more direct feedback on planning and the more realistic insight into pupils’ thinking in the instructional setting TS, should constitute the most advantageous treatment for students as novices in the topic “PCK on probability”.

Hypothesis 3. Cognitive preconditions (PCK, CK, intelligence, all at T1) do not moderate the effects of the different treatments, i.e., there are no interaction effects between the treatments and cognitive preconditions. The reason for this is that we tried to design the intervention such that the need for prior knowledge or cognitive preconditions was as low as possible (cf. Section 5.2).

The specific focus was on the development of PCK on probability from T1 (baseline) to T2, T3, and T4, respectively.

8. Method

The present study is part of the project “Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Motivation – Probability as a Topic in Primary Teacher Education” (Drollinger-Vetter & Buff, 2014). As part of their preservice teacher education, students must complete the course “Research and development”. The study was conducted within this module, in the third semester. Up until that point, students had not yet worked on the topic of “probability” as part of their study program.

8.1. Sample

In total, $N = 512$ students from the study course “primary teacher education” at the Zurich University of Teacher Education (PHZH) participated in the study in 2015 and 2016 (for details, see Section 8.3).

8.2. Intervention

The intervention is described in detail above (Section 6). Students were randomly allocated to the individual treatments and were unaware of their allocation in advance. Group sizes were as follows: CUTS: $n = 104$, CUCM: $n = 101$, TATS: $n = 103$, TACM: $n = 104$.

The lecturers who carried out the intervention were experienced lecturers in mathematics education. According to Evens et al. (2015), using experts as leaders increases the effectiveness of interventions. The lecturers of the four treatment groups completed a special 4-day training course prior to the intervention. For the “CU” and “TA” instructional settings, on the first day of the intervention, the lecturers were randomly divided into two groups. The training focused on PCK and CK on probability as well as the special features of the respective instructional setting. In both instructional settings, the content, processes, tasks, and materials were predefined. The handling of the tasks was also standardized; for example, it was specified which central points had to be addressed during the discussions of the tasks solved by the students. On the second day of the intervention, in the “TS” and “CM” instructional settings, the lecturers only had an organizational function. The exact procedure of the two instructional settings was fixed in standardized scripts. Content, materials, and assignments were specified. The scripts governed, in detail, what to say and when, and how and when to set which tasks. The lecturers were not permitted to provide any assistance in terms of content. The training on the second day of the intervention consisted of discussing the scripts together and clarifying open

questions.

On both days, the control group (CG: $n = 100$) took part in courses of the same length, but on the topic of “Experimentation – discover mathematics” (Philipp, 2013). The topic of “probability” was not addressed in these courses. Table 7 illustrates the time schedule of the present study as well as the data collected at each time point.

8.3. Measures

In the following, we describe the measures used in the present study.

Control group and treatment groups: Membership of the individual groups was specified using dummy coding. According to the respective objective of the analyses, different groups formed the reference group (0).

Gender and educational background: 414 (81%) of the participants were female (0) and 98 (19%) were male (1). 215 (42%) did not have grammar school-leaving qualifications (0) and 297 (58%) had grammar school-leaving qualifications (1).

Cohort: 239 (47%) participated in 2015 (0); 273 (53%) participated in 2016 (1).

Intelligence at T1: IQ was assessed using the IST screening, which is an intelligence structure test (Liepmann, Beauducel, Brocke, & Nettelstroth, 2012). The test consisted of 60 tasks. Reliability (Cronbach’s α) for the overall test amounted to $\alpha = .717$.

Mathematics self-concept (MSC) at T1: MSC was measured using four items (Fischer, Buff, & Drollinger-Vetter, 2018): “I think I’m quite good at mathematics”, “Mathematics is something I’m not very good at”, “Mathematics is easy for me”, “I have problems in mathematics”. The items were rated on a 7-point scale (1 = completely true, 7 = not at all true). Reliability was $\alpha = .881$.

Pedagogical content knowledge and content knowledge on probability: To the best of our knowledge, there was no specific test to measure PCK on the topic of “probability” at primary school level at the time of planning the present study. Therefore, we developed the PCK test, which comprised tasks on all three subcomponents mentioned in Section 2.1. Examples include, e.g., expected pupil answers on a given task, advantages and disadvantages of certain protocol techniques and whether a particular task is part of the contents taught in primary school. The construction of the items was inspired by the literature mentioned in Section 4 and Table 2.

As various studies have shown that teachers often possess little CK (see Section 4), the CK test was designed to correspond closely to school knowledge: It encompassed typical CK from primary to secondary school level, with only a few concepts at grammar-school level (e.g., distributions), as well as theoretical knowledge on empirical and theoretical probability. The tasks originated from curricular material, were inspired by the literature on teacher education (e.g., Eichler & Vogel, 2013; Krüger, Sill, & Sikora, 2015), were adapted from existing studies (6 items; e.g., hospital problem from Tversky & Kahneman, 1974), or were

self-developed for the purpose of the present study.

The development of both tests encompassed interviews with students, gathering expert opinions, as well as pilot testing with other students one year prior to the start of the study. Both tests were paper-and-pencil tests. An example item for each test can be found in Appendix A (Table 1A).

The PCK test consisted of 49 tasks across all four measurement time points, while the CK test comprised 36 tasks. Of these, 45 tasks in the PCK test and 20 in the CK test had an open response format and were coded by two persons who were specially trained for each individual task. For each task, following a training phase, the interrater reliability (Cohen’s K) was calculated for approximately 20% of the respective students’ answers and was confirmed: $Md_K = .882$ for the PCK tasks and $Md_K = .984$ for CK tasks. K ranged between .767 and 1.00 in both tests.

The two tests were scaled separately, each across all four measurement time points. In both cases, a Rasch model was specified. The four measurement time points were each linked pairwise to the next by means of anchor items (common-item design cf. Hartig & Kühnbach, 2006; Reckase, 2009; Vale, 1986). For both tests, one-dimensionality was established for each measurement time point separately, and the stochastic independence of the items was demonstrated across all measurement time points (Q_3 statistics $< .40$; cf. Yen, 1993). The reliabilities for both tests were within an acceptable range for newly developed tests: $EAP_{PCK} = .61$; $EAP_{CK} = .65$ (comparable to the values reported in other studies, e.g., Bruns, Hagen, & Gasteiger, 2023). The correlation between the PCK test and the CK test at T1 was $r = .33$ ($p < .001$).

8.4. Data analysis

Descriptive analyses, reliability calculations, as well as cross-tabulations with subsequent χ^2 tests were performed using IBM SPSS 27. The scaling of the achievement tests was undertaken using the TAM package (Robitzsch, Kiefer, & Wu, 2017) in R. All other analyses were performed with Mplus 8 (Muthén & Muthén, 2017), using the robust maximum likelihood estimation (MLR), which is robust against violations of normality assumptions (Marsh et al., 2018). Full information maximum likelihood estimation (FIML) was used to handle missing data (Enders, 2010; Jelčić, Phelps, & Lerner, 2009). The extent of missing data in the present study was kept within narrow limits. Overall, 2.73% of the data were missing.

MSC was modeled using the four items as latent indicators. All other variables in the analyses were manifest variables. Model fit was assessed using the comparative fit index (CFI), the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), and the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR). Model fit is seen as good if CFI $\geq .95$ and RMSEA and SRMR $\leq .05$ (Brown, 2015; Little, 2013).

Fig. 1 shows the general analysis model. Deviations from the general analysis model are described at the beginning of each of the corresponding results sections. In all analyses concerning the three hypotheses, as presented in Fig. 1, we considered a series of covariates that have partly proven to be relevant for PCK development (cf. Baumert et al., 2010; Blömeke, Buchholtz, et al., 2014; Blömeke, Suhl, & Kaiser, 2011; Friedrichsen et al., 2009; Kleickmann et al., 2013): PCK and CK on probability, intelligence, mathematics self-concept, gender, educational background, and cohort.

Group membership (dummy-coded), gender, educational background, and cohort were already known prior to the first data collection. The T1 data collection was conducted at the start of the study (cf. Table 7). All variables at T1 were predicted by all prior variables (symbolized by an arrow from the left block to the middle block). PCK at T2, T3, and T4 acted as central dependent variables (right block). These three variables were in turn predicted by all prior variables (symbolized by the two arrows from the left or middle block to PCK at T2–T4). Of primary interest were only the effects of group membership – controlling for all variables in the left and middle blocks – on PCK at T2, T3, and T4,

Fig. 1. General analysis model.

Table 8
Treatment groups vs. control group.

	PCK T2		PCK T3		PCK T4	
	<i>b</i> [95% CI <i>b</i>]	<i>t/p</i>	<i>b</i> [95% CI <i>b</i>]	<i>t/p</i>	<i>b</i> [95% CI <i>b</i>]	<i>t/p</i>
	<i>r</i> [95% CI <i>r</i>]		<i>r</i> [95% CI <i>r</i>]		<i>r</i> [95% CI <i>r</i>]	
CG vs. CUTS	0.97 [0.78, 1.15] 10.17/.000 .41 [.34, .48]		1.14 [0.96, 1.33] 12.06/.000 .48 [.41, .54]		0.65 [0.43, 0.87] 5.71/.000 .25 [.16, .33]	
CG vs. CUCM	0.85 [0.65, 1.05] 8.31/.000 .35 [.27, .42]		1.09 [0.90, 1.29] 11.17/.000 .45 [.37, .51]		0.49 [0.27, 0.71] 4.34/.000 .19 [.11, .27]	
CG vs. TATS	0.87 [0.66, 1.07] 8.37/.000 .35 [.27, .42]		0.93 [0.74, 1.12] 9.55/.000 .39 [.32, .46]		0.52 [0.30, 0.75] 4.51/.000 .20 [.11, .28]	
CG vs. TACM	1.01 [0.83, 1.20] 10.81/.000 .44 [.36, .50]		0.93 [0.75, 1.12] 9.77/.000 .40 [.32, .47]		0.42 [0.20, 0.63] 3.78/.000 .17 [.08, .25]	
PCK T1	0.26 [0.18, 0.33] 6.83/.000 .29 [.21, .37]		0.27 [0.19, 0.34] 7.15/.000 .31 [.22, .38]		0.23 [0.15, 0.31] 5.64/.000 .25 [.16, .32]	
CK T1	0.18 [0.11, 0.24] 5.16/.000 .23 [.14, .31]		0.13 [0.07, 0.19] 4.23/.000 .19 [.10, .27]		0.21 [0.13, 0.29] 5.18/.000 .23 [.14, .31]	
Math Self-Concept T1	-0.01 [-0.08, 0.06] -.017/.869 -.01 [-.09, .08]		0.05 [-0.02, 0.12] 1.41/.160 .06 [-.02, .15]		-0.01 [-0.09, 0.08] -0.13/.895 -0.01 [-.09, .08]	
Intelligence T1	0.12 [0.04, 0.19] 2.96/.003 .13 [.04, .22]		0.09 [0.03, 0.16] 2.71/.007 .12 [.03, .20]		0.10 [0.02, 0.18] 2.39/.017 .11 [.02, .19]	
Gender	-0.20 [-0.37, -0.03] -2.27/.023 -.10 [-.19, -.01]		-0.23 [-0.40, -0.06] -2.59/.010 -.12 [-.20, -.03]		-0.12 [-0.29, 0.06] -1.29/.196 -.06 [-.14, .03]	
Educational background	0.21 [0.07, 0.34] 2.95/.003 .13 [.04, .22]		0.18 [0.05, 0.32] 2.69/.007 .12 [.03, .20]		0.06 [-0.10, 0.22] 0.69/.492 .03 [-.06, .12]	
Cohort	-0.02 [-0.15, 0.11] -0.24/.812 -.01 [-.10, .08]		0.07 [-0.05, 0.19] 1.17/.244 .05 [-.03, .14]		-0.06 [-0.21, 0.10] -0.74/.460 -.03 [-.12, .05]	
<i>R</i> ²	.38		.41		.25	
<i>p</i>	.000		.000		.000	

Note. The group mentioned first in the comparisons forms the reference category (0) of the pair comparisons. PCK = pedagogical content knowledge, CK = content knowledge.

CG = control group (*n* = 100), CUTS = treatment group “Core components of understanding/Tutorial situation” (*n* = 104), CUCM = treatment group “Core components of understanding/Curricular material” (*n* = 101), TATS = treatment group “Tasks/Tutorial situation” (*n* = 103), TACM = treatment group “Tasks/Curricular material” (*n* = 104).

b = unstandardized path coefficients, [95% CI *b*] = 95% confidence interval of *b*, *t* = *t*-value; *p* = probability value; *r* = effect size *r*, [95% CI *r*] = 95% confidence interval of *r*; *R*² = variance explained. *N* = 512.

respectively. Therefore, PCK at T2, T3, and T4 were correlated with one another. It should be noted that PCK at T1 was present in all analyses. The effects of group membership – as with all other predictors – regarding PCK at T2, T3, or T4, can thus be interpreted as effects regarding the change in PCK in the time periods T1–T2, T1–T3, and T1–T4, respectively. The fit of the general analysis model was very good: $\chi^2(41) = 52.585, p = .106$; SCF = 1.001; CFI = .995; TLI = .985; RMSEA = .023; CFI = .997 [.000, .040]; SRMR = .016.

The question of potential interaction effects between the treatments and the cognitive preconditions (cf. Hypothesis 3) was analyzed using a multiple-group model, subsequent equality constraints and model comparisons. For each of the five groups, an analysis model corresponding to that of the general analysis model (without dummies) was simultaneously specified. The fit of the multiple-group model was acceptable: $\chi^2(177) = 219.579, p = .016$; SCF = 0.968; CFI = .979; TLI = .955; RMSEA = .048; CFI = .535 [.022, .068]; SRMR = .053.

The presence of potential interaction effects was individually tested stepwise for each cognitive precondition (PCK, CK, intelligence, all at T1), for each time period (T1–T2, T1–T3, T1–T4), and for each pair comparison, by setting the corresponding paths of the respective cognitive precondition to be equal (equality constraints) in each of two groups. Following this, the model fits of the two multiple-group models

without and with constraints ($\Delta df = 1$) were tested for statistically and practically significant differences in each case. If, in the case of the models with equality constraints, a worse model fit results, then an interaction effect is present.

With respect to the model comparisons mentioned above and with regard to the test of measurement invariance (cf. Section 8.5), χ^2 difference tests were applied. With the use of the estimator MLR, the conventional χ^2 difference test is not appropriate. Instead, therefore, a modified, so-called scaled χ^2 difference test was conducted (retrieved [09.06.22] from <http://www.statmodel.com/chidiff.shtml>).

8.5. Measurement invariance

Regarding MSC, multiple-group measurement invariance was tested. The fit of the configural, metric, and scalar invariance models was acceptable. The loss of fit in the metric and scalar invariance models was not significant (for detailed information see Appendix B Supplementary Material Table 1B). As such, it can be concluded that the MSC scale showed scalar invariance between the different groups.

8.6. Effect sizes and confidence intervals

The Results section presents, in addition to the statistical significance of an effect, its effect size (ES) as a measure of the practical significance as well as the corresponding confidence interval (CI). In this context, Baguley (2009) calls for the use of a *simple effect size* (see also Nakagawa & Cuthill, 2007). In the case of regression analyses, this would be the unstandardized regression coefficient b of a predictor. Regarding the CI values for b (in brackets), the concern is with asymptotic CI values (default in Mplus). In addition, the Pearson correlation coefficient r was calculated as a standardized effect size based on the t -values of the unstandardized regression coefficients b , following the procedure of Nakagawa and Cuthill (2007). The procedure considers that several predictors were always present in all analysis models, and the results in the present case were always based on an N of 512. In the case of model comparisons, the effect size r was calculated in line with the procedure by Rosenthal and DiMatteo (2001).

Basically, the CI values for the effect size r are calculated using a noncentral t -distribution (Smithson, 2001). However, Goulet-Pelletier and Cousineau (2018) showed that the calculation of CI values based on noncentral or central t -distributions are equivalent if the group size of each group in a between-group design is larger than 20 (see also Fritz, Morris, & Richler, 2012). Accordingly, the CI values for the effect size r were calculated in accordance with Borenstein (2009) based on central t -distributions (for an alternative see Nakagawa & Cuthill, 2007).

According to Cohen (1988), effect sizes $.10 \leq r < .30$ are seen as small, $.30 \leq r < .50$ as moderate and $.50 \leq r$ as large. However, these interpretations are controversial and should therefore be viewed with caution and taken only as a rough guide (Baguley, 2009; C. J. Hill, Bloom, Black, & Lipsey, 2008; Lakens, 2013; McGrath & Meyer, 2006).

9. Results

9.1. Preliminary analyses: randomization

The question of potential differences between the control group and the individual treatment groups, and between the individual treatment groups, regarding the characteristics of gender, educational background, and cohort was tested using a series of cross-tabulations and χ^2 square tests. To this aim, each of two groups were compared with regard to one characteristic. In no case did statistically significant and/or practically relevant differences emerge.

If randomization is successful, there should also be no differences between the groups regarding the characteristics at T1 (PCK, CK, intelligence, MSC). While this was the case, gender and educational background were found to have significant positive effects on the four dependent variables. However, this is of no further interest for the present context (for detailed information see Appendix B Supplementary Material Table 2B).

9.2. Main analyses

9.2.1. Development of PCK: treatment groups vs. control group (hypothesis 1)

We expected that from T1 to each of the subsequent measurement time points T2, T3, and T4, PCK would develop more favorably in all treatment groups than in the control group. The results of the analyses are presented in Table 8. It is apparent that in all treatment groups and in all time periods (T1–T2, T1–T3, T1–T4), PCK developed statistically significantly more positively than in the control group. Moreover, these positive effects were also of practical relevance. Compared to the control group, PCK developed especially positively in the period T1–T2 in the TACM group ($b = 1.01$, $p < .000$, $r = .44$) and in the periods T1–T3 as well as T1–T4 in the CUTS group ($b = 1.14$, $p < .000$, $r = .48$; $b = 0.65$, $p < .000$, $r = .25$).

Furthermore, the analyses revealed that apart from MSC at T1 and

cohort, all other variables – PCK, CK, and intelligence (all at T1), as well as gender and educational background – showed statistically significant independent effects regarding the development of PCK in most cases. With the exception of the effects of PCK and CK, however, these were of rather low practical relevance.

In summary, the findings confirmed Hypothesis 1, even when controlling for some of the predictors relevant for the development of PCK.

9.2.2. Development of PCK: comparison between individual treatment groups (hypothesis 2)

According to Hypothesis 2, we expected that from T1 to each of the subsequent measurement time points T2, T3, and T4, PCK would develop more favorably in the CUTS treatment group than in the other treatment groups.

In a first step, all dummy variables (D1–D4) in the general analysis model were changed such that the treatment group CUTS formed the reference group (0). The control group remained in the model but was of no further interest. Analogously, in further steps, it was additionally tested whether a different treatment group – compared to each of the other treatment groups – might be characterized by more favorable PCK developments. Regarding the dummy variables (D1–D4), the same procedure as that described above was employed. Finally, all treatment groups were compared with one another in the different time periods, and all treatment groups as well as the control group remained in the analyses. All other remaining variables in the general analysis model likewise remained in the model (cf. Fig. 1). Note that in all of these analyses, only the effects of the dummy variables changed; the values of the effects of the remaining variables (as well as R^2) can be found in Table 8. Due to space restrictions, in the following we describe only those group comparisons for which statistically significant and/or practically relevant differences were found:

The treatment group CUTS, which was of primary interest here, only showed a statistically significant more favorable PCK development than the other treatment groups in three out of nine cases (CUTS vs. TATS T1–T3: $b = -0.21$ [-0.40, -0.02], $t = -2.15$, $p = .031$, $r = -.10$ [-.18, -.01]; CUTS vs. TACM T1–T3: $b = -0.21$ [-0.40, -0.02], $t = -2.20$, $p = .028$, $r = -.10$ [-.18, -.01]; CUTS vs. TACM T1–T4: $b = -0.23$ [-0.46, 0.00], $t = -1.97$, $p = .049$, $r = -.09$ [-.17, .00]). However, if one considers the size of these effects and in particular their CIs, these differences are not of practical relevance. In view of these findings, Hypothesis 2 could not be confirmed. In terms of the remaining comparisons between treatment groups, no differences in the development of PCK emerged.

9.2.3. Interaction effects treatment groups \times cognitive preconditions (hypothesis 3)

Hypothesis 3 stated that cognitive preconditions – PCK, CK, and intelligence (all at T1) – do *not* moderate the effects of the treatments, meaning that the impact of a treatment is independent of the students' cognitive preconditions. As described in Section 8.4, this hypothesis was analyzed by means of a multiple-group model comprising five groups, equality constraints, and subsequent model comparisons.

Of the total of 54 potential interaction effects, none proved to be statistically significant and/or practically relevant. Thus, Hypothesis 3 can be seen as confirmed: Cognitive preconditions did *not* moderate the effect of the individual treatments.

10. Discussion

The present study investigated how to foster the development of PCK on probability in primary teacher education. The topic of “probability” has only recently become a part of the primary school curriculum in the German-speaking part of Switzerland. The study was an experimental, longitudinal field study with four treatment groups and one control group. Such a design is rather rare in research on fostering PCK (Evans et al., 2015). To the best of our knowledge, the present study is unique with regard to the topic of promoting the development of PCK on

probability in primary school teacher education.

10.1. Main findings

10.1.1. Hypothesis 1

In line with the first hypothesis, compared to the control group, PCK developed more favorably in all four treatment groups and in each time period (T1–T2, T1–T3, and T1–T4). Moreover, all of these differences in development were statistically significant and of practical relevance. The findings did not change when controlling for influencing variables regarding the development of PCK (e.g., CK, intelligence, gender, and educational background). Thus, [Hypothesis 1](#) was confirmed. We consider this finding to be important given that the topic of “probability” is seen as difficult to learn and to teach ([Batenero & Diaz, 2012](#), see Section 4). Furthermore, it has long been known that increased CK as a consequence of teaching on topic of “probability” is not a given ([Batenero & Diaz, 2012](#); [Jones et al., 2007](#); [Shaughnessy, 1992](#)). The same likely applies for PCK on “probability”, as intervention studies on promoting PCK similarly do not inevitably reveal positive effects (see [Evens et al., 2015](#)). Our study also demonstrated that even a short intervention can be successful, which, in our view, is indicative of the PCK-related quality of the treatments.

10.1.2. Hypothesis 2

According to the second hypothesis, we expected PCK to develop more favorably in the CUTS treatment group than in the other treatment groups. However, our findings did not confirm [Hypothesis 2](#). While there were some indications of statistically significant more favorable developments in this treatment group, they were of little practical relevance. We also tested whether a different treatment may prove to be superior to the others, but this was not the case. These findings suggest that different ways are similarly effective in terms of acquiring PCK on “probability” and there is no single “silver bullet” for success. With respect to [Batenero’s \(2020, p. 686\)](#) open research question “How best to educate teachers to become competent in the teaching of probability?”, based on the present findings, and in line with [Shaughnessy \(1992\)](#), there appears to be no clear answer. Studies examining PCK across different mathematics topics have reached similar findings (e.g., [Krauss, Baumert, & Blum, 2008](#), see Section 3). Given that no one treatment was superior, there seems to be some leeway for lecturers to design teaching in the area of “PCK on probability”. At least within the framework of the four treatments examined here, they are free to choose according to their own personal preferences.

What might be the reasons for the similarly high effectiveness of the four treatments?

Instructional settings CU and TA in the Introduction: Due to the variety of tasks worked on in the instructional setting TA, the students may have become similarly acquainted with the core components of understanding to the students in the instructional setting CU, in which core components of understanding were addressed more explicitly and intensively.

Instructional settings TS and CM in the Consolidation: First, the advantages of direct teaching experience in preservice teachers might be similarly achieved indirectly, through suitable selected curricular material. (Note that the curricular material in the instructional setting CM referred precisely to the tasks from the planning). In this case, curricular material would act as a type of second-hand teaching experience. Second, only one lesson (approx. 45 min) was taught in the tutorial situation, which may not have been sufficient to fully bring the (postulated) learning potential of the CUTS treatment to fruition in terms of fostering PCK. Future studies should therefore examine whether clearer positive effects are shown with a longer teaching unit.

10.1.3. Hypothesis 3

With regard to the third hypothesis, we assumed that different cognitive preconditions on the part of the students would *not* moderate

the effect of the individual treatments. There were no statistically significant and/or practically relevant interaction effects in any case, and [Hypothesis 3](#) was therefore confirmed. Accordingly, the effect of the treatments was independent of differences in the cognitive preconditions at the start of the study (cf. also [Harr, Eichler, & Renkl, 2014](#)). It appears that – as intended – we were able to design the treatments so as to enable optimal benefit for all students, independently of their cognitive preconditions (PCK, CK, intelligence, all at T1).

Combined with the results regarding [Hypothesis 2](#), this means that irrespective of the cognitive preconditions of the students, there are various PCK-related ways to design instruction in the area of “PCK on probability” from which to choose, and they seem to be similarly effective. However, this does not rule out that there may be other characteristics that have moderating effects regarding the individual treatments (e.g., beliefs about probability).

10.2. Strengths and limitations

One of the strengths of the present study lies in its design: We conducted a quantitative, experimental, longitudinal field study with four treatment groups and a control group, included four measurement time points, and considered several covariates that are relevant for the development of PCK, in a substantial sample of over 500 students. The reviews by [Depaepe et al. \(2013\)](#) and [Evens et al. \(2015\)](#) revealed that such designs are rather rare in research on PCK development. A further strength of the study is that we were able to demonstrate that PCK can be fostered even by a short intervention and independently of cognitive preconditions, and that this effect can be detected even about ten weeks later. Moreover, the treatments were designed such that they can be transferred to regular teacher education.

However, several limitations of the present study need to be mentioned. As the sample was not representative, the question arises of the extent to which the results can be transferred to other institutions of teacher education, especially those in which the study program design deviates (strongly) from that at the PHZH.

As mentioned above, the PCK test in particular, and to a lesser extent also the CK test, were newly developed. For both tests, it was very challenging to construct tasks with sufficient variance and without floor or ceiling effects, which had content validity, were comprehensible for the students, and could be reliably coded. While the reliabilities of the two overall tests were acceptable for newly developed tests, they nevertheless can, and indeed should, be improved. In particular, more tasks per measurement time point might allow for various different subcomponents of PCK to be captured, which was not possible in the present case. While the tasks related to three different subcomponents of PCK, ultimately there were too few tasks per subcomponent to be able to form subscales. [Grossman \(1990\)](#) pointed out that different sources of PCK could foster different subcomponents of PCK in different ways (cf. also [Depaepe et al., 2020](#)). By using different subscales, it would be possible to examine whether the individual treatments have differing effects on the various components of PCK. Another possible limitation could be that the conceptualization and operationalization of PCK was primarily based on the cognitive perspective. The reason for this is that the focus was on PCK, which is more likely to be acquired in formal teacher education. Furthermore, it should be noted that PCK courses seem to be especially effective when the concept of PCK is explicitly introduced at the start of the intervention, and its usefulness and relevance is pointed out ([Evens et al., 2015](#); [Kind, 2009](#)). While this was not the case in the present treatments, it can be recommended for future studies.

In our view, future research should focus more strongly on the entire chain of effects from pre-service and/or in-service teacher education, via teaching quality, to pupil learning ([Depaepe et al., 2020](#)). Furthermore, it is necessary to analyze in greater detail the role that CK as well as motivational variables play in PCK acquisition over time. Based on this and further analyses, it should be possible to gain deeper insights into

the mechanisms of PCK acquisition and how it can be fostered.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Barbara Drollinger-Vetter: Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Alex Buff:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Frank Lipowsky:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Kathleen Philipp:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Sebastian Vogel:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis.

Funding

The present work was supported by the Swiss National Science

Appendix A

Table 1A
Sample items capturing CK and PCK

PCK item	What misconception is typical for the following task? Two dice are rolled. The values of the two dice are added together. What are the probabilities of the sums?														
CK item	A fair die is rolled 20 times. The result is shown in the tally chart.														
	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> <td>6</td> <td>total</td> </tr> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td>###</td> <td>###</td> <td> </td> <td>###</td> <td>20</td> </tr> </table>	1	2	3	4	5	6	total			###	###		###	20
1	2	3	4	5	6	total									
		###	###		###	20									
	<p>Please fill in: The absolute frequency of rolling a 4 is _____. The relative frequency of rolling a 4 is _____.</p>														

Appendix B. Supplementary Material

Supplementary Material to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2025.104953>.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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Foundation [grant number 156711].

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the project team, all lecturers, students, teachers and their classes who contributed to the realization of the study. We would also like to thank Sarah Mannion de Hernandez for translating the article into English.

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